

Individual Work Performance and Job Satisfaction: Life Satisfaction as a Mediator

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Abstract

Individual work performance includes actions aligned to the goals of organization. Life and job satisfaction are the positive emotions related to the life as a whole and the job. Does life satisfaction mediate the relationship between individual work performance and job satisfaction? The research question guided this study based on survey method of data collection from 2303 employees of Nepal working in various industries like medicine, education, service, engineering, or labor. Findings showed that life satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between the individual work performance and job satisfaction, indirect effect, $ab = .09$, direct effect, $c = .39$. Nearly one-fifth effect on job satisfaction was from mediation, and it was partial. The conclusion is that the concept of positive spillover in occupational health psychology gains more confidence, and employers need to help employees enhance their life satisfaction if they

want satisfied persons at their workplace

Keywords : Job satisfaction, Life satisfaction, Work performance, Task performance, Counterproductive behaviors

Introduction

The individual behaviors or actions that are oriented towards the goals of organization refer to individual work performance (Koopmans et al. , 2016). There are different types of performance and multiple types of well-being (Taris & Schaufeli, 2014) such as life satisfaction and job satisfaction. Promoting both is the goal of the organization but there is a tradeoff sometimes.

Individual Work Performance

Work performance refers to the individual actions that contribute to the goals of organization (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). Individual work performance (IWP) has major three dimensions: task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive behaviors (Koopmans et al. , 2016). Other dimensions like adaptive performance (Koopmans et al. , 2011) are also possible. Task performance refers to the skills with which employees perform the tasks central to their job. Behaviors that support the context of functioning of technical core mean the contextual performance. Counterproductive behavior is the behavior that harms the well-being of organization. A study (Adhikari, 2020) found that emotionally intelligent employees score low in measure of counterproductive behavior. Declarative knowledge, skill and motivation may be the determinants of work performance (McCloy et al. , 1994). Performance is considered a positive variable in organizational behavior.

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Job Satisfaction

The job attitude that refers to the evaluation about job and its aspects is job satisfaction. In other words, it refers to the positive feelings gathered from experience of doing a job and being related to it. Job satisfaction depends on factors related to job design (like feedback, autonomy, meaningfulness of job), employee (like emotional disposition), social environment at work (like supervisor relationship, social support) and growth opportunities (Levy, 2017). A study (Adhikari, 2018) had found that salary increase significantly increases job satisfaction in Nepali employees to a small extent. It is also significantly correlated with work motivation (Maharjan, 2012). Job satisfaction leads to organizational commitment (Timalsina et al. , 2018), more performance, less absenteeism, and lower counterproductive behaviors (Levy, 2017). Job satisfaction is not only affected by work-related factors like individual work performance but also by life-related factors such as life satisfaction.

Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction is the extent to which one finds their life full, meaningful, rich or of high quality (VandenBos, 2015). Life satisfaction is influenced by factors such as friendship quality and network (Amati et al. , 2018), financial satisfaction (Diener & Diener, 2009), self-efficacy (Wright & Perrone, 2010), spending quality time with family and nature, recreation, break from work for refreshment (Sirgy et al. , 2011), religiosity promoting social interaction (Okulicz-Kozaryn, 2010) and job satisfaction (Judge & Watanabe, 1993). Some aspects of work life like individual work performance and job satisfaction are likely to affect life satisfaction.

Relationship between Individual Work Performance, Job Satisfaction, and Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction is significantly associated with work performance (Jones, 2006). It is likely to predict work performance (like organizational citizenship behavior) and vice versa. Growth opportunities, social support at work, appreciation and management related to job satisfaction can predict life satisfaction (Filiz, 2014). Life satisfaction is a significant correlate rather than the cause of job satisfaction (Judge & Watanabe, 1993). The correlations between individual work performance, life satisfaction and job satisfaction are clearly understood but the understanding about life satisfaction mediating the relationship between individual work performance and job satisfaction has not come yet. This study targets to determine if life satisfaction can be the mediator. Figure 1 shows the conceptual model for the analysis of this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual model for the mediation

Theoretical Framework

Positive spillover is the process in which experiences in a role can enhance the quality or performance of another role (Bakker & Derks, 2010). On the basis of this theory, life satisfaction can enhance the level of job satisfaction by the process of family-work enrichment. Many studies support spillover hypothesis (Rain et al. , 1991). For example, marital satisfaction and home affect are influenced by daily job satisfaction (Ilies et al. , 2009). Life satisfaction significantly predicts the job satisfaction (Schmitt & Pulakos, 1985). This study aims to test if life satisfaction can enhance job satisfaction. Specifically, the hypothesis being tested is: life satisfaction mediates the relationship between individual work performance and job satisfaction.

Methods

This quantitative study has a survey design. The data was collected through the network of BA (Psychology) students in a government-owned college in Kathmandu.

Instruments

English version of Individual Work Performance Scale (Koopmans et al. , 2016) was used to measure individual work performance and its components: task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive behaviors. It is a valid test (Koopmans et al. , 2014) that has 18 items with the last five measuring counterproductive behaviors, the first five measuring task performance, and the remaining measuring the contextual performance. The total score was found out by summing task and contextual performance scores and subtracting counterproductive behavior score. Each item in it can be rated in 5-point scale (0 meaning seldom to 4 meaning always). The satisfaction with life scale (Diener et al. , 1985) was used to measure life satisfaction. It is a 7-point Likert scale with five items, each item rated from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The higher score in it means more life satisfaction. Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire Short Form (University of Minnesota, 1977) was used to measure job satisfaction. It is a 5-point Likert scale with options ranging from very dissatisfied to very satisfied. The higher score in it means more job satisfaction. A questionnaire to collect sociodemographic details of the participants was also used.

Participants

Total of 2303 participants ($M_{age}=31.52$, $SD_{age}=8.80$) took part in this survey. More than half of the participants (54.3%) were male ($M_{age}=32.79$, $SD_{age}=9.11$) and the remaining (44.9%) were female ($M_{age}=29.99$, $SD_{age}=8.12$). More than four-fifths (82.2%) participants were Hindu, 10.9% were Buddhists, and the remaining were from other religions or atheists. Among all, 5% did not reveal their ethnicity, 29% were Baun, 19.6% were Chhetri, 17.4% were Newar, 7.4% were Tamang, 4.3% were Magar, and the remaining others were from diverse ethnicity like Tharu, Sherpa, Rai, Limbu, Gurung, Janjati, Dalit, Muslim and Madhesi. One-third (33.8%) participants were teachers, 9.6% were from medical field, 20.7% (including civil servants) did some service jobs, 7.6% identified themselves as workers such as seamster or home maid, 2.2% were army, 2.0% were tour/trekking guide, and the remaining were managers, CAs, drivers, engineers, trainers, audit associates, accountants, social workers, researchers, artists, writers, consultants, attendants, businesspersons, and so on. The sociodemographic item to fill up profession was open-ended.

So, the answers were eclectic. Nearly one-third (32. 2%) participants lived in joint families, 66. 8% lived in nuclear families, and the remaining did not reveal the family type. More than half (57. 8%) participants were married, 40. 7% were single and the remaining did not reveal their marital status.

Procedure

The research was planned as survey. The questionnaire was made including demographic details and three psychological tests. A network of students was deployed to collect data. They approached the participants. The informed consent was taken from them. After the employees from various organizations completed the questionnaire, their data was entered into Excel and organized in it.

Data Analysis

Model 4 of PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2018) in SPSS was used for mediation analysis with 50000 bootstrap samples. Data from Excel was imported into SPSS and analyzed.

Results

Table 1 shows summary of job satisfaction, life satisfaction and individual work performance. The means, standard deviations and quartiles have been reported.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of the job and life satisfaction, and individual work performance

Variable	M	SD	Q1	Q2	Q3
Job satisfaction	71. 95	11. 06	66. 00	73. 00	80. 00
Task Performance (a)	14. 80	3. 59	13. 00	15. 00	17. 00
Contextual Performance (b)	22. 27	5. 74	18. 00	23. 00	27. 00
Counterproductive behavior (c)	6. 99	4. 79	3. 00	6. 00	10. 00
Individual work performance (a+b-c)	30. 09	8. 91	24. 00	30. 00	37. 00
Life satisfaction	23. 10	5. 56	20. 00	23. 00	27. 00

Table 2 shows the bivariate correlations between the variables. All correlations were signif cant. So, they are able to predict each other.

Table 2

Bivariate correlations between the job satisfaction, individual work performance and life satisfaction

	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Job satisfaction	(. 88)					
2	Task Performance (a)	. 369**	(. 75)				
3	Contextual Performance (b)	. 246**	. 621**	(. 79)			
4	Counterproductive behavior (c)	-. 155**	. 094**	. 215**	(. 81)		
5	Individual work performance (a+b-c)	. 391**	. 753**	. 779**	-. 362**	(. 83)	
6	Life satisfaction	. 356**	. 243**	. 190**	-. 103**	. 276**	(. 75)

Note. ** means the correlation is significant at . 01 level of significance; figures in parentheses along diagonal are the Cronbach's alphas for related measure

Each component of IWP was tested as a predictor in the mediation model with life satisfaction as mediator. With task performance, both direct, $c = .92$, 95% CI [.81, 1.04] and indirect, $ab = .21$, 91% CI [.17, .26] effects were significant. Nearly one-fifth (18.58%) of the effect was from mediation and it was partial. Task performance predicted life satisfaction significantly, $B = .38$, $t = 12.01$, $p < .001$ with 5.90% variance. Task performance, $B = .92$, $t = 15.75$, $p < .001$ and life satisfaction, $B = .56$, $t = 14.82$, $p < .001$ predicted job satisfaction significantly with 21.17% variance. With contextual performance, both direct, $c = .36$, 95% CI [.28, .43] and indirect, $ab = .12$, 95% CI [.09, .15] effects were significant. Nearly one-fourth (24.8%) effect was from mediation. Contextual performance significantly predicted life satisfaction, $B = .18$, $t = 9.27$, $p < .001$ with 3.6% variance. Job satisfaction was significantly predicted by contextual performance, $B = .36$, $t = 9.49$, $p < .001$ and life satisfaction, $B = .64$, $t = 16.48$, $p < .001$ with 15.96% variance. With counterproductive behaviors, both direct, $c = -.28$, 95% CI [-.36, -.19] and indirect, $ab = -.08$, 95% CI [-.12, -.05] effects were significant. Nearly one-fourth (22.8%) effect was from mediation. Counterproductive behaviors significantly predicted life satisfaction, $B = -.12$, $t = -4.98$, $p < .001$ with 1.07% variance. Job satisfaction was significantly predicted by counterproductive behaviors, $B = -.28$, $t = -6.16$, $p < .001$, and life satisfaction, $B = .68$, $t = 17.68$, $p < .001$ with 14.09% variance.

With total score of individual work performance also, the mediation model was significant: direct effect, $c = .39$, 95% CI [.35, .44], indirect effect, $ab = .09$, 95% CI [.07, .11]. Nearly, one-fifth (18.96%) effect was from mediation. Individual work performance significantly predicted life satisfaction, $B = .17$, $t = 13.77$, $p < .001$ with variance of 7.61%. Job satisfaction was significantly predicted by individual work performance, $B = .39$, $t = 48.27$, $p < .001$ and life satisfaction, $B = .53$, $t = 14.01$, $p < .001$ with 21.93% variance.

Conclusion and Discussion

The conclusion is that life satisfaction can mediate relationship between individual work performance (or all its three domains) and job satisfaction. The positive spillover effect is clearly seen and the confidence in the concept has increased. The practical implication is that organizations need to focus to increase employees' life satisfaction because it is a significant contributor of job satisfaction. Past studies have provided the similar conclusions. Work-life balance can contribute to both life and job satisfaction (Haar et al., 2014). Work-life conflict is negatively associated with life and job satisfaction (Marič et al., 2021).

There are few limitations in this study. The psychological test taken to assess work performance may have low content validity in that work performance can cover more domains including technical performance, communication, motivation, leadership and management performance (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015) than it considered. The study does not deal with specific occupations and is a generic analysis. The future studies can test the same hypothesis in particular occupations. The sample was made by convenient method. So, the generalizability should be cautiously considered. Some sampling bias may affect the external validity. For example, the sample may be inclined more to urban areas and private employees. The future studies can check if other life-related aspects such as marital satisfaction, parents-children relationship, and settlement arrangement can mediate the relationship between individual work performance and job satisfaction or relationship between other work-related variables.

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लोक सेवा आयोग

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लेख रचनाको लागि अनुरोध

यस आयोगबाट अर्धवार्षिक रूपमा प्रकाशित हुने निजामति सेवा पत्रिकामा लेख रचना प्रकाशित गराउन चाहने लेखक महानुभावहरूलाई आयोगमा प्राप्त हुने गरी लेख रचना पठाउन हार्दिक अनुरोध गरिन्छ । सार्वजनिक सेवा सम्बन्धी विविध पक्ष, आर्थिक गतिविधि र योजनावद्ध विकाससँग सम्बद्ध मौलिक, खोजपूर्ण, विचार प्रधान तथा अनुसन्धानमूलक विषय समावेश भएका लेख रचनाहरू प्रकाशनको निमित्त ग्राह्य हुनेछन् । प्रकाशनार्थ पठाइने लेख रचनाको सुरुमा सारांश, अन्त्यमा निष्कर्ष र लेखमा प्रयोग भएका सन्दर्भ सामग्रीहरू संलग्न भएको हुनुपर्नेछ । यस पत्रिकामा प्रकाशनको लागि पठाइएका लेख रचनाहरू अन्यत्र प्रकाशन गर्नुपरेमा प्रकाशकको पूर्व स्वीकृति लिनुपर्नेछ । पत्रिकामा प्रकाशनार्थ प्राप्त लेख रचनाहरू स्वीकार गर्ने वा नगर्ने अधिकार सम्पादक मण्डलमा रहनेछ ।

यस पत्रिकामा प्रकाशित हुने लेखहरूमा त्यक्त गरिएका विचारहरू लेखकका निजी विचार भएका हुनाले ती लेखहरूले लेखक कार्यरत वा लेख प्रकाशन गर्ने निकायको प्रतिनिधित्व गर्ने छैन ।

सम्पादक मण्डल

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अध्यक्ष

गीता कुमारी होमेगाई

सह-सचिव

सदस्य

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सम्पादकीय

निजामती सेवाको पदमा नियुक्तिको लागि उपयुक्त उम्मेदवार छनोट गरी सिफारिस गर्ने तथा सुरक्षा निकाय र संगठित संस्थाहरूको लिखित परीक्षा सञ्चालन गर्ने संवैधानिक अधिकार प्राप्त लोक सेवा आयोगले स्वतन्त्र, निष्पक्ष र तटस्थ रूपमा आफ्नो कार्यसम्पादन गर्दै आएको छ । आयोग स्थापनाकालदेखि हालसम्म सर्वसाधारण जनताको आशा र भरोसाको केन्द्रको रूपमा रही आएको छ । यही विश्वासको आधारमा नेपालको संविधानले लोक सेवा आयोगको कार्य जिम्मेवारी समेत थप गरेको छ ।

मुलुक संघीय शासन प्रणाली कार्यान्वयनको चरणमा रहेको वर्तमान सन्दर्भमा सम्पूर्ण निजामती कर्मचारी तथा अन्य सरकारी सेवाका कर्मचारीहरूको आशा र भरोसाको केन्द्रविन्दुमा रही आफ्नो अभिभावकत्व निर्वाह गर्न एवं स्थापनाकाल देखिको विश्वास समेतलाई जोगाई राख्न आयोग सामु चुनौति थपिएको छ ।

प्रस्तुत अंकमा सार्वजनिक सेवा, निजामती प्रशासन तथा विकास प्रशासनसँग सम्बन्धित लेखहरू रहेका छन् र यसबाट अनुसन्धानकर्ता, अध्येता तथा सार्वजनिक व्यवस्थापनका विषयमा सरोकार राख्ने सबैलाई सहयोग पुग्ने अपेक्षा गरिएको छ । यस पत्रिकालाई अझ उत्कृष्ट बनाउन पाठकवर्गबाट सुझाव तथा पृष्ठपोषणको अपेक्षा गर्दछौं । पत्रिकाको लागि लेख रचना उपलब्ध गराई सहयोग गर्नुहुने विद्वान लेखकहरूप्रति कृतज्ञता प्रकट गर्दै आगामी दिनहरूमा समेत यस्तै सहयोग प्राप्त हुनेमा विश्वस्त छौं ।

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